
A Critical Review of Empirical Studies on Women's Representation in Indonesian Textbooks

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to analyze the discourse elements of women's power relations in the text. This study used data from Indonesian integrated textbooks for 2nd-grade elementary schools. In addition, textbooks are a form of research. This study uses field data analysis methods. Data collection techniques include checklists, interviews, and documentation of language forms in textbooks. The theory used in this research is discourse analysis theory (Dijk 1993). The results of this study show that the text contains discourse elements such as microstructure, macrostructure, and superstructure that refer to male power relations. Microstructure contains grammatical elements that include references, deletions, and conjunctions. In Indonesian elementary school integrated subject textbooks, the macro elements are context, situation, and context of culture. Character values are implicitly described by text characters. The microstructure, macrostructure, and superstructure of the data show the dominance of women's relations.

1. Introduction

The sociological perspective is the development of the theory of social construction, community interaction, and the social power of society. Sociology is the scientific study of humans in social life and social processes that exist in society. Sociology studies how humans adapt to the environment and how humans socialize and interact with other humans in society. One of the sub-fields of social science that maps problems and understands the reality of gender issues in social life in relation to

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the use of language can be reviewed in sociolinguistic studies. Sociolinguistics is the relationship between language and the people who use it. Sociolinguistics is one of the interdisciplinary between sociology and linguistics which are closely related to one another. The language or expressions expressed by a person reflect the attitude of the speaker (Holmes, 2001).

An interesting phenomenon in public communication is the difference in the use of linguistic markers from a gender perspective. The gender perspective in question is the use of forms of linguistic markers that are differentiated based on gender and social roles. (Lakof, 2004) states that there are many things that underlie the emergence of differences between women and men, one of which is the difference in language. Research that focuses on the relationship between language and gender was pioneered by (Lakof, 2004) who put forward a theory about the existence of women's languages through his book *Language on Women's Place*.

The same thing was conveyed by (Wardhaugh, 2006) who emphasized that the differences in the use of language in question can be observed from the differences in the characteristics of the language used between men and women. Gender is considered a characteristic that cannot be exchanged between women and men (Ulfah et al., 2019). Several gender issues in textbooks have received considerable attention to overcome some of the stereotypical gender messages conveyed in the teaching and learning (Rohmawati & Putra, 2022). If gender inequality becomes a natural thing in the world of education to be included in textbooks, it will greatly contribute to the thinking of students. Textbooks are widely recognized as objects of social reproduction and the spread of dominant ideologies (Babaii & Sheikhi, 2018). Among the existing pedagogical tools, textbooks are one of the pedagogical tools used in the teaching and learning (Eva, 2015). Textbooks are very important in determining gender roles and status in society (Alam & Badshah, 2022). With the help of this textbook, students get knowledge and information from outside the teacher (Arraman & Hazmi, 2018). Textbooks are a tool for sharing knowledge and for teachers to guide students through books (Alexopoulos et al., 2022).

The previous study that analyzed the same topic conducted by (Ullah et al., 2014) stated found that There are still gender stereotypes in textbooks. Gender bias in textbooks is important because the information contained in textbooks is an important instrument of power that shapes the ways children think about themselves and society. Thus, the central aim of this review is to confirm that persistent gender bias in children's literature tends to reinforce and legitimize the gender system. Another review comes from (Ryan, 2022) this study examines ten studies from seven countries in the region and highlights how discriminatory patterns still exist in national textbooks. It then examines how political and policy solutions address gender equality in national curricula and discusses the implications of CEDAW for women and girls. Another study is from (Rodríguez et al., 2022). This article provides an overview of recent international studies in the field of textbooks, educational materials, and physical education. The results show the multiplicity of studies, especially ideological discourse. Methodologically, the most common was a content analysis of textbooks and materials. The study was from (Hashemian et al., 2022) entitled *A Critical Review on the Reproduction of Dominance and Gender Discrimination Relation in Textbooks of Iran's Educational System*. The analysis of the research results reinforces the hypothesis but shows that the content of the textbooks, establishing a submissive attitude in female students, makes them accept dominant relationships and gender discrimination in adulthood.

This research would examine gender power relations studied in elementary school textbooks. The elementary school textbooks used as data sources were the Indonesian Language Integrated Thematic companion books for grade II. The book is considered sufficient to represent the linguistic forms of gender power relations that are examined. These books are used by elementary school

students in the learning process. The book is in accordance with the ongoing National Curriculum and is used as a compulsory book in schools. The contents of the book present the power relations between women and men which are examined more fully to find differences in linguistic markers of power between women and men based on discourse analysis, sociology of gender regarding the division of labor and their implications for students.

This study analyzes gender power relations in integrated thematic textbooks for Indonesian Elementary Schools, with the hope of finding novelty empirically and theoretically in the field of linguistics, especially in the field of Sociolinguistics. Gender power relations are in fact stated implicitly and explicitly in textbooks containing the gender power displayed. With discourse analysis, it will be known the microstructure and macrostructure of language form gender power relations in textbooks. This would certainly find clear discrimination in the division of sexual labor that has been shown clearly in the text. This study reveals implicit and explicit linguistic markers in class II Indonesian integrated thematic books. The linguistic markers found in this study refer to the theory of Critical Discourse Analysis which focuses on analyzing the microstructure, macrostructure, and superstructure. The problem analyzed in this study is How are the types and forms of language microstructural power relations in the integrated thematic textbooks of Indonesian Elementary Schools? This research will certainly enrich the development of linguistics so that it would be able to produce new innovations in sociolinguistic theory studied more clearly with discourse analysis to analyze gender power relations, especially in student textbooks.

2. Materials and Methods

With background problems observed in society, this research was researched with the use of qualitative research methods. The purpose of this research is to identify and analyze the forms of discourse structure that it consists of micro, macro, and superstructure on book text lessons in elementary school grade 2. This study uses theory discourse analysis (Dijk, 1993). However for strengthening the theory of microstructure used theory (Sumarlam, 2013) which classifies microstructure with cohesion markers that are grammatical cohesion and coherence lexical. At the same time, the theory (Naim, 2012) is used to support the macrostructural analysis of which character is seen in the text. The source of this research data is a book text Indonesian grade 2. In addition to data sources primary, too used secondary data sources such as interviews and surveys with students, parents, and teachers as consumers' conversations.

3. Results and Discussions

This data reveals the gender role of women which is represented dominantly in the discourse. The analysis is divided into three namely microstructural, macrostructural, and superstructure analysis which are analyzed in full below.

a. Microstructural Analysis

Microstructural analysis of discourse is analyzed to find grammatical cohesion and lexical cohesion in discourse. The grammatical cohesion is found to determine the amount and structure of the discourse as a whole. The form of the discourse structure analyzed in the microstructure can reveal the participants (actors) and gender variables that are spread out in the discourse (Cf. Latupeirissa et al., 2019). The following is a microstructural analysis of the data.

 Data: Discourse on *Lemper* Cake

Hari ini, ibu akan membuat kue lempet. Ibu meminta bantuan Nina. Nina bersemangat membantu ibu. Ini adalah pengalaman pertama Nina membuat kue lempet. Nina membantu ibu memberikan abon sebagai isi lempet. Namun, ia tidak sengaja menjatuhkan abon ke lantai. Nina segera membersihkannya dan meminta maaf kepada ibu. Nina kurang hati-hati. Ibu memaafkan kesalahan Nina. Mereka lalu melanjutkan kegiatan mereka.

Today, Mom will make lempet cake. Mom turned to Nina for help. Nina is passionate about helping her mom. This is Nina's first experience making lempet cakes. Nina helped her mother give shredded meat to fill in the lempet. However, he accidentally dropped abon to the floor. Nina immediately cleaned it up and apologized to Mom. Nina wasn't careful. Mother forgave Nina's mistakes. They then continued their activities.

Integrated Thematic Companion Book for Grade II SD/MI (Indradi:113)

Grammatical cohesion includes references, substitutions, ellipsis and conjunctions. In the text found 13 clauses that compose the text. To facilitate analysis, these clauses are coded clause 1 to clause 13 and participant code with the letter (P). The distribution of grammatical cohesion found in the text is shown in the following table.

Table 1: Distribution of Grammatical Cohesion Markers

No	Clause	Reference	Substitution	Ellipse	Conjunction
1	Today, <i>mother</i> will make a cake lempet	P1			
2	<i>Mother</i> ask for help <i>Nina</i>	P1, P2			
3	<i>Nina</i> enthusiastic	P2			
4	ØP2helping mother	P2			
5	This is the first experience <i>Nina</i> make slime cakes	P2			
6	<i>Nina</i> help <i>mother</i>	P2, P1			
7	ØP2give shredded as the contents of the lempet.	ØP2		ØP2	

8	However, <i>him</i> accidentally dropped <i>abon</i> to the floor.	P2			However
9	<i>Nina</i> immediately clean it	P2			
10	And ØP2 apologize to <i>mother</i>	ØP2, P1		ØP2	and
11	<i>Nina</i> less careful.	P2			
12	<i>Mother</i> forgive mistakes <i>Nina</i>	P1, P2			
13	<i>They are</i> then continue the activity <i>them</i>	P1, P2			Then
	Amount	P1 : 6 P2: 12		ØP2 : 2	However, and, then

Based on the table distribution that has been described, there are 13 clauses that compose the text. Based on 13 clauses, there are 18 references that make up the text. The reference consisted of two participants namely P1 (Mother), P2 (Nina). Most participants who gave roles in the text were Participant 2 (Nina) and supported by participant 1 (Mother). While there are two forms of ellipsis in the text which refer to Participant 2. Several conjunctions are used in constructing the text such as the conjunction however, *and*, *then*, *then*. The conjunction is used to connect one clause with another clause to make it unified.

Referencing or reference is one type of grammatical cohesion in the form of a specific lingual unit that refers to another lingual unit (or a reference) that precedes or follows it. The type of grammatical cohesion of reference is classified into three types, namely persona reference, demonstrative reference, and comparative reference (Sumarlam, 2008:23). Persona reference is realized through pronouns (personal pronouns), which include the first person (persona I), second (persona II), and third (persona III) both singular and plural.

- (1) Today, *mother* will make a cake *lemper*.
- (2) *Mother* ask for help *Nina*.
- (3) *Nina* enthusiastic
- (4) ØP2 help *mother*.
- (5) This is the first experience *Nina* makes slime cakes.
- (6) *Nina* helps *mother*
- (7) ØP2 give shredded as the contents of the *lemper*.
- (8) However, he accidentally dropped *abon* to the floor.

In clause (1) there is a participant's mother as a subject. The subject in the initial clause is explained explicitly by referring to the character in the text. Based on the characters that have been mentioned, the gender of the characters in the text is classified as female. Mother in the discourse it is attached to the gender of women with their role as parents who do chores at home making *lemper* cakes. In clause (1) said *mother* followed by the predicate and object in one complete sentence. Clause (2) still uses the participant's *mother* as a subject and is followed by a predicate with a verb request. Participant (2) appears in clause (2) as an object. Participant (2) *Nina* is represented by the female gender in accordance with its role of helping mothers make slime cakes. Based on the characters attached to the participant (2) and the peculiarities of gender variables such as making *lemper* cakes,

and helping mothers, the participant (2) can be classified as female gender. Clause (3) uses the subject Nina as a participant (2) followed by a predicate with a verb *enthusiastic*. In clause (4) there is an ellipsis on the subject that refers to Nina. In full clause (4) should be *Nina helps mom*. In clause (5) there is a participant (2) *Nina* explicitly used in clauses.

Something similar is found in clause (6), Participant (1) and participant (2) are used explicitly in clause (6). In clause (7) there is an ellipsis on the subject that refers to the participant (2) *Nina*. In full clause (7) should be *Nina gave shredded meat as the contents of the lempur*. Clause (8) is a continuation of clause (7) which is connected by conjunctions *However*. Conjunction *However* is a type of conjunctive conjunction. After the conjunction, there is a singular third-person pronoun *him* which refers to other elements that are in the discourse mentioned earlier. The singular persona III pronominal form contained in clause (8) refers to Participant 2 *Nina*. With such characteristics, then *him* is a type of grammatical cohesion of endophoric reference (because the reference is in the text) which is anaphoric (because the reference is mentioned before or the antecedent is on the left).

- (9) *Nina* immediately clean it
- (10) *and* ØP2 apologize to *mother*.
- (11) *Nina* is less careful.
- (12) *Mother* forgives *Nina* mistakes.
- (13) *They* then continue the activity them.

In clause (9) participant (2) *Nina* expressed explicitly. Say *Nina* functions as the subject of a sentence and is followed by a predicate with the verb clean *it*. In clause (10) using conjunctions *and*. The Conjunction *and* used to connect clauses (9) and clauses (10) which have an equivalent relationship. In clause (10) use the ellipsis for the subject. Ellipses are used to achieve economic value in the use of language. The ellipsis in clause (10) is a word omission *Nina* as a subject. In clause (11) explicitly uses the character's name *Nina* as a subject. This is similar to clause (12) which explicitly uses the word *mother* as a subject. The subject in clause (13) uses the pronominal person III in the free form plural *them*. Word *them* is an endophoric reference because the reference is in the discourse. This endophoric reference is anaphoric because the reference has been mentioned before or the antecedent is on the left. The pronominal form of the third person plural of the independent form that has been mentioned in clause (13) refers to the first participant's *Mother* and the second participant *Nina* which has been mentioned in the previous clause.

Discourse cohesiveness is not only supported by grammatical aspects or grammatical cohesion but also supported by lexical aspects or lexical cohesion. Lexical cohesion is the relationship between elements in discourse systematically. Lexical cohesion in discourse can be divided into six types, namely repetition, synonymy, collocation, hyponymy, anatomy (opposite words), and equivalence. Of the six types of lexical cohesion, not all types of lexical cohesion found in the text are synonyms. In this text, only synonyms are found as markers of lexical cohesion. Synonyms can be interpreted as another name for the same object or thing; or expressions that have more or less the same meaning as other expressions. Synonymy is one of the lexical aspects to support discourse cohesiveness. Synonyms function to establish a relationship of commensurate meaning between certain lingual units and other lingual units in the text.

*However, he accidentally dropped the floss into the floor. Nina immediately cleaned up and apologize to Mom. **Nina** was less careful. **Mother** forgives Nina's mistake. **They** then continue their activities.*

Based on the quotations in the text, using lexical cohesion forms of synonymy with morphemes *her*. Morpheme *her* on the word *clean it* synonymous with the words *floor* which has been mentioned in the previous clause. Morpheme *her* in the word *cleaning it* has a cohesive relationship based on lexical aspects with the choice of words that match the word *floor*. Semantically, the word *floor* which has been mentioned in the previous clause is not repeated in the next clause. But synonymous with morpheme *her* on the word *clean it*. In addition, synonyms are found in the word *mother* and *Nina* which is synonymous with the word *them*. Say *them* on cause *they* **then continue** their *activities* have semantic cohesion with words *mother* and *Nina* mentioned in the previous clause.

b. Macrostructural Analysis

After previously the linguistic elements have been clearly analyzed in microstructural analysis, the next analysis focuses on macrostructural analysis in the text which includes context analysis. Context analysis includes cultural context and situational context. In the context of the situation includes the physical context, epistemic context, and social context. The various contexts are not strictly separated as separate analyses of lexical elements in the microstructure but are analyzed interrelated with one another to build a unified whole of discourse.

Cultural Context

The cultural context is the basis for understanding the meaning of discourse. In Indonesian society, the gender of women and gender of men have differences gender *differences* basic. Community culture interprets gender as the division of roles between men and women, and until now it is still a living culture of the community. Based on the representational text, the role of women dominates the composition of the text. The role of women is manifested in the form of women's division of labor in the text, emotions, and characters of the characters in the discourse. This can be seen in the following text.

Data: Discourse on Lemper Cake

Today, Mother will make lempers. Mom turned to Nina for help. Nina is eager to help mom. This is Nina's first experience making lempers. Nina helped her mother give shredded meat to fill in the lempers. However, she accidentally dropped it on the floor. Nina immediately cleaned it up and apologized to Mom. Nina wasn't careful. Mother forgave Nina's mistakes. They then continued their activities.

Based on the discourse, it is stated that there are two figures in the discourse namely Mother and Nina. The gender role of women that is highlighted in the discourse is in the gender variable attached to both. The women's gender variables that are explicitly stated in the clause are the mother's role, the mother's attitude, and baking. Gender roles that exist in society from the past until now, look at the concept of patriarchy, giving rise to unequal roles. This division of labor is a sociological phenomenon in a society that has developed since ancient times and remains current until now. Women in the domestic sphere and men in the public sphere. The division of domestic labor expressed in the discourse can be seen in the quotation *Today, mom will make lempers. Mom turned to Nina for help*. Based on these quotes, the role *mother* focused on domestic roles. The domestic role that is expressed explicitly in these quotations is the activity of cooking or making lempers. This work is considered not to require excessive physical work that is appropriate for a mother in accordance with her role as a parent. The role of parents in this case is to meet the needs

of food and drink in the family for their children and husband. Figure *Mother* and *Nina* are represented as female characters attached to the gender role of women. This can be seen from the peculiarities of the nature and character expressed in the discourse. Figure *Mother* and *Nina* revealed to have a gentle, forgiving, and compassionate characters. This can be seen in the quote *Nina helped her mother give shredded meat to fill in the lemper*. This quote shows that *Nina* has a helpful attitude. On quote, *However, he accidentally dropped abon to the floor. Nina immediately cleaned it up and apologized to her mom* representing that *Nina* has a good heart and admits mistakes. Temporary Mothers are represented as parents who have a loving and forgiving attitude. This can be seen in the quotation others *forgave Nina's mistakes*.

Many people think that this is something that is natural, given, and taken for granted without any comment. This will look normal if a mother does cooking and baking activities. The division of tasks in the household such as cooking is the division of labor for the female gender. This becomes common when expressed explicitly in the discourse. So far, female workers are valued and considered as someone who is gentle and have weaker physical strength than male workers. The female characters expressed in the discourse provide a clear picture that the sexual division of labor is still developing in society. Gender women are considered appropriate to do the domestic work assigned to them. In addition to domestic work making cakes, it implicitly states that *Mother* and *Nina* have weak physical strength compared to the father in the family structure. Thus, the father's role in making *lemper* cake is not raised in the discourse, with the assumption that the father is going to the office and is not at home when the characters are making the cake. Another assumption that can be drawn is that the father may rest when the two characters make the *lemper* cake.

The female gender variable expressed in the discourse has strengthened the unequal gender roles of women and men. In other words, if students are faced with a discourse that contains clear gender stereotypes, then students will believe this is a particular learning experience. Students can remember events in the discourse as long-term long-term *memory* based on learning experiences that have been read in the discourse. Thus, the stereotype of the division of domestic labor based on gender can cause girls to believe that the stereotype of gender exists only in the division of domestic labor. This affects the way children see themselves and their abilities and prevents children from exploring themselves well. Social construction always places women in a lower position than men, for example during the Dutch colonial period, women were always locked up in the house, and their role was only to do household chores and also do kitchen affairs. This construction has carried over to the present day, women choose to be housewives who look after their children and take care of household chores.

Situational Context

The context of the situation is seen as a barrier to the meaning of the discourse. The context of the situation studied in this analysis is limited to the physical context, epistemic and social context which is considered from several interpretations (personal, locational and temporal) as well as the principle of analogy.

Data: Discourse on Lemper Cake

Today, Mom will make *lemper cake*. Mom turned to *Nina* for help. *Nina* is passionate about helping her mom. This is *Nina's* first experience making *lemper* cakes. *Nina* helped her mother give shredded meat to fill in the *lemper*. However, he accidentally dropped abon to the floor.

Nina immediately cleaned it up and apologized to Mom. Nina wasn't careful. Mother forgave Nina's mistakes. They then continued their activities.

The physical context includes three important aspects, namely the place where an event occurs, the object or topic being discussed, and the actions of the participants in the communication. (1) the reality of the situation (events, circumstances, processes) expressed in this discourse occurs in the house.

This is expressed in quotes *Today, mom will make lempur cake*. This quote implicitly states that the activity of making *lempur cakes* tends to be done at home. Based on the temporal principle, it can be seen that this event occurred during the day. Making *lempur cakes* requires adequate lighting and electrical energy. Thus, the activity of making cakes is usually done in the afternoon to the afternoon. (2) The topic of conversation in the communication is the relationship between parents and daughters namely Nina. The two figures in the discourse represent gender roles that are expressed implicitly and explicitly. The gender role of women in discourse is expressed explicitly in quotations *Today, mom will make lempur cake. Mom turned to Nina for help. Nina is passionate about helping mom*. Making *lempur cakes* is usually done by a woman and it is very rare for men to participate in this activity. (3) The actions or behavior of the participants in the event broadly included (a) the mother would make *lempur cakes*, (b) Nina was eager to help the mother, (c) Nina helped the mother provide shredded meat as the contents of the *lempur*, (d) she accidentally dropped shredded to the floor, (e) Nina immediately cleaned it up and apologized to mother. (f) Nina is not careful. Mother forgave Nina's mistakes.

Epistemic context relates to background knowledge that is both known by speakers and speech partners. In the events of the discourse, speakers, and partners say. In the events of the discourse, the speaker *Mother*, and speech partner Nina understands that the activities carried out require good diligence and accuracy. *Nina is happy to help Mother doing baking activities. They happily do activities together. This can be seen in the quote Mom turned to Nina for help. Nina is passionate about helping her mom. This is Nina's first experience making lempur cakes*. The word is excited proves that Nina is happy to help *Mother* making cake.

Social context relates to social relations and settings that complement the relationship between speakers and hearers. Social relations between *Mother* and Nina is the relationship between children and parents *Mother* have a higher social status relationship than Nina in family relationships. Temporary *Nina* has a lower social status relationship compared to *Mother* Consideration of high and low social status in the discourse is a consideration for Nina more respect for his mother. In this discourse, *Nina* is represented as a child who likes to help and respect parents. This is seen in the quotation *Mom turned to Nina for help. Nina is eager to help her mom*. Based on this quote, *Nina* is represented as children who respects and obey their parents. Attitude representation *Nina* based on another social status can be seen in quotes *he accidentally dropped abon to the floor. Nina immediately cleaned it up and apologized to Mom*. The quote explicitly reveals that the character *Nina* and *Mother* both know that *Nina* made a mistake and should apologize. The attitude of obedience and respect for older people is more dominantly represented by the female gender in the discourse.

c. Superstructure Analysis

The schematic of the discourse is usually arranged with general categories such as orientation, complication, and resolution. The schematic structure emphasizes the parts that come first and the parts that come later as a strategy to hide important information. The following is a schematic analysis of the discourse.

-	Title
<p>Today, mom will make lempur cake. Mom turned to Nina for help. Nina is passionate about helping mom. This is Nina's first experience making lempur cakes.</p>	Orientation
<p>Nina helped her mother give shredded meat to fill in the lempur. However, he accidentally dropped abon to the floor. Nina immediately cleaned it up and apologized to mom. Nina wasn't careful.</p>	Complications
<p>Mother forgave Nina's mistakes. They then continued their activities.</p>	Resolution

The schematic arrangement of discourse in text consists of orientation, complication, and resolution. The discourse in the data does not contain the title of the discourse so that readers do not understand the topic of the discourse to be disclosed. The discourse begins with an orientation by conveying the background and events that will be carried out by the characters. In the orientation section, the author introduces the main character in the discourse namely *the mother* and *Nina*. In the complication section, the events presented by the author are disclosed. The author reveals the activities together to make a cake. This section also disclosed with events Nina made the mistake of accidentally dropping the shredded cake filling on the floor. Seeing this incident, the mother does not express excessive emotion by scolding Nina. Attitude *Nina* after dropping the floss, namely by immediately apologizing to his mother. Figure *Mother* This meme *Nina* who are not careful. The form of resolution in the discourse is Nina cleaning the cake that fell on the floor and apologizing to his mother. This discourse is then closed with *Mother forgiving Nina* and they continue their activities.

The affirmation of women's gender roles in the discourse is expressed explicitly in the orientation section and implicitly expressed in complications and resolutions. In the orientation section, women's gender roles are expressed explicitly by the character's *mother* as an introduction to the main character. The gender classification of women is indicated by the gentle, forgiving, and kind attitude of a mother. This is confirmed by the name of the character's *mother* which shows that the main character in the discourse is the female gender. Meanwhile, in the complications and resolution sections, it is expressed implicitly by showing women's characters in the discourse. The gender role of women is expressed by the attitude and character of women who are patient, forgiving, and gentle. This can be seen implicitly in the complication and resolution section. Based on the results of this analysis, it can be concluded that the female gender in the analysis of the superstructure of the

text is dominant. In other words, the representation of women's gender is expressed in almost the entire contents of the discourse.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the discourse analysis of the text, explicit and implicit representations of gender are found. This is evidenced by the findings of data analysis on microstructure, macrostructure, and superstructure. Microstructural analysis of data concludes that: Based on the analysis of microstructure, there are 13 clauses that compose the text. The results of the analysis of grammatical cohesion state that there are 18 references that make up the text. Based on the analysis of lexical cohesion, it is found that synonymous forms are used in the text. Synonyms function to establish an equivalent meaning relationship between certain lingual units and other lingual units in the text. In microstructural analysis, the gender role of women is evidenced by the arrangement of lingual units expressed by the dominant characters in the text based on the distribution of participants. Based on the analysis of macrostructure, discourse is analyzed based on the cultural context and the context of the situation.

The women's gender variables that are explicitly stated in the clause are the mother's role, the mother's attitude, and baking. Gender women are considered appropriate to do the domestic work assigned to them. In addition to domestic work making cakes, it implicitly states that *Mother* and *Nina* have weak physical strength compared to the father in the family structure. (3) Based on the superstructure analysis, it is found that the schematic arrangement of the discourse is orientation, complication, and resolution. The gender roles of women expressed in discourse are mostly found in orientation, complications, and resolutions. The affirmation of women's gender roles in the discourse is expressed explicitly in the orientation section and implicitly in the complications and resolution sections. Based on this analysis, it is concluded that the gender role of women in discourse is represented explicitly in almost all parts of the discourse.

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